

Editorial Note

Due to the pandemic event in the 2020 only the single issue (Vol. 11; Iss. 1-2) of the Review has been published and the first issue of the 2021 (Vol. 12 Iss. 1) has been published with a delay. First, I thank the Authors of these two issues for their appreciable patient.

Second, I am pleased to inform that the Vol. 11, Iss. 1-2 - 2020 of the Review of Economics and Institutions is the first valuable contribution of the renewed team of Managing Editors. Since January 2020 Simona Bigerna (University of Perugia) and Amedeo Argentiero (Kore University of Enna) have joined Paolo Polinori (University of Perugia) and Lewis S. Davis (Union College) and will serve as new Managing Editors for the incoming years.

With the 2019 Fall issue Antonio Minniti (University of Bologna), Andrea Presbitero (International Monetary Fund) and Francesco Venturini (University of Perugia) have completed their office and have left the managing board.

I wish to warmly thank Antonio, Andrea and Francesco for their contribution to the Journal and for the work done in these years.

Perugia, 7/12/2020

The Editor in Chief
Prof. Carlo Andrea Bollino

Recommended Citation

Bollino, C.A. (2021). Editorial Note. *Review of Economics and Institutions*, 12(1), Article 0. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5763547

Retrieved from <http://www.rei.unipg.it/rei/article/view/331>